

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 137

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 137

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 137:1 By the ^arivers of Babylon, There we sat down and ^bwept, When we remembered Zion. ² Upon the ^{1a}willows in the midst of it We ^bhung our ²harps. ³ For there our captors ^{1a}demanded of us ²songs, And ^bour tormentors mirth, <i>saying</i>, “Sing us one of the songs of Zion.”</p>	<p>Psa. 137:1 עַל נְהַרֹת אַבְדֹן וְכָל שָׁם יִשְׁבְּנוּ גַם-בְּכִינֹו בְּזָכְרֵנוּ אֶת- צִיּוֹן : ² עַל-עֲרָבִים בְּתוֹכָהּ תָּלִינוּ כַּנְּרוֹתֵינוּ : ³ כִּי שָׁם נִשְׁאַלֹנוּ שׁוֹבֵינֵנוּ דְבַר-יִשְׂרָאֵל וְתוֹלְלֵינוּ שְׂמֵחָה נִשְׂרוּ לָנוּ מִנְשִׁיר צִיּוֹן : ⁴ אֵיךְ נִשְׂרֵי אֶת- נְשִׁיר-יְהוָה עַל אֲדָמַת נֶכֶד : ⁵</p>
<p>Psa. 137:4 How can we sing “the LORD’S song In a foreign land? ⁵ If I “forget you, O Jerusalem, May my right hand ¹forget <i>her skill</i>. ⁶ May my “tongue cling to the roof of my mouth If I do not remember you, If I do not ^{1b}exalt Jerusalem Above my chief joy.</p>	<p>אִם-אֲשַׁכַּח יְרוּשָׁלַם תְּשַׁכַּח יְמִינִי : ⁶ תִּדְבַק-לְשׁוֹנִי אֶל-חִפְיִ אִם-לֹא אֲזַכֵּרְכִי אִם-לֹא אֶעֱלֶה אֶת-יְרוּשָׁלַם עַל רֹאשׁ שְׂמֵחָתִי : ⁷ זָכֹר יְהוָה אֶל-בְּנֵי אֲדוֹם אֶת יוֹם יְרוּשָׁלַם</p>
<p>Psa. 137:7 Remember, O LORD, against the sons of “Edom The day of Jerusalem, Who said, “Raze it, raze it ^bTo its very foundation.” ⁸ O daughter of Babylon, you ^{1a}devastated one, How blessed will be the one who ^brepays you With ²the recompense with which you have repaid us.</p>	<p>הָאֲמָרִים עָרוּ אֶעְרוּ עַד הַיְסוֹד בָּהּ : ⁸ בְּת-בְּכָל הַשְׂדֵדוֹת אֲשֶׁר־יִשְׁשָׁלֶם-לָךְ אֶת-אֲמוֹלֶךְ שְׂנֵמֶלֶת לָנוּ : ⁹ אֲשֶׁר־יִשְׂאֲחֹז וְנִפְּץ אֶת-עַלְלֶיךָ אֶל-הַסֵּלַע :</p>

<p>⁹ How blessed will be the one who seizes and "dashes your little ones Against the rock.</p>	
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References

Psalm 137:1

^aEzek 1:1, 3

^bNeh 1:4

Psalm 137:2

¹Or *poplars*

²Lit *lyres*

^aLev 23:40; Is 44:4

^bJob 30:31; Is 24:8; Ezek 26:13

Psalm 137:3

¹Lit *asked*

²Lit *words of song*

^aPs 80:6

^bIs 49:17

Psalm 137:4

^a2 Chr 29:27; Neh 12:46

Psalm 137:5

¹I.e. become lame

^aIs 65:11

Psalm 137:6

¹Lit *cause to ascend*

^aJob 29:10; Ps 22:15; Ezek 3:26

^bNeh 2:3

Psalm 137:7

^aPs 83:4-8; Is 34:5, 6; Jer 49:7-22; Lam 4:21; Ezek 25:12-14; 35:2; Amos 1:11; Obad 10-14

^bPs 74:7; Hab 3:13

Psalm 137:8

¹Or *devastator*

²Lit *your recompense*

^aIs 13:1-22; 47:1-15; Jer 25:12; 50:1-46; 51:1-64

^bJer 50:15; 51:24, 35, 36, 49; Rev 18:6

Psalm 137:9

^a2 Kin 8:12; Is 13:16; Hos 13:16; Nah 3:10

Targum

Psa. 137:1 By the rivers of Babylon, there we sat down, also we wept, as we were remembering Zion. ² On the willows in her midst we hung our harps. ³ For there the Babylonians who captured us asked us to utter the words of songs; and our despoilers, because of [their] joy, were saying, “Sing for us some of the songs you used to utter in Zion.” ⁴ At once the Levites cut off their thumbs with their teeth, and say, “How can we sing the praise of the LORD on profane land?” ⁵ The voice of the holy spirit replies and says, “If I forget you, O Jerusalem, I will forget my right hand.” ⁶ My tongue will cleave to my palate, if I will not remember you; if I will not elevate the memory of Jerusalem above the principal joy of my temple. ⁷ Said Michael, prince of Jerusalem, “Remember, O LORD, the people of Edom, who laid waste Jerusalem, who say, ‘Destroy, destroy, to the foundations of it.’ ” ⁸ Said Gabriel, prince of Zion to the despoiling Babylonian mother, “Happy he who gives back to you evil for what you did to us.” ⁹ Happy he who takes and smashes your children on a rock.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm conveys the intense mourning of a once joyous nation shrouded in the gloom of being in exile from their homeland. The people remembered the glory of Mount Zion and sadden because of its destruction at the hands of the Babylonians. There is a custom for the bridegroom to recite this verse under the wedding canopy as he awaits his bride, to fulfill the Jew's eternal vow not to fail to elevate Jerusalem above his foremost joy (verse six).

Notes on this Psalm

Verse nine is one that is usually misunderstood. The author did not want to see children's heads smashed against rocks. This was a known curse spoken against an enemy. It is actually a request to the LORD that the enemy be destroyed because the enemy attacked the LORD's people. This Psalm should remind the reader that anything that the LORD gives can be taken away. Why would the LORD take a gift away? As the people of Judah discovered when they violated the LORD's Law, especially pagan worship in the LORD's Temple, then the LORD will react. In this case, He removed his protection from Judah and the Babylonians conquered it. Always remember that everything one has is from the LORD.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

